

PARTICIPATION OF WOMEN IN PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION OPPORTUNITIES FOR EXPANSION

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Abstract Since the independence of Uzbekistan until today, the participation of women in state administration can be divided into different periods. In particular, we all know that in New Uzbekistan there is an opportunity to freely discuss the issue of women's rights and gender equality. Especially the fact that the main nature of the laws and legal documents adopted at the level of the president and the cabinet of ministers are aimed at strengthening the participation of women in state administration and protecting women from violence also determined the main direction of the important turn. And this in itself indicates that it is necessary to move forward now, there is no way back.

Key words: New Uzbekistan, gender equality, national parliament, local government system, women's rights and freedoms, position in the family, elections, parliament, local councils, governorships, United Nations, social and political activity.

Many reforms aimed at ensuring gender equality, increasing the rights and freedom, value and status of women are being implemented in new Uzbekistan.

In particular, "For the first time in the history of Uzbekistan, the number of women in the national parliament has reached the level corresponding to the recommendations of the United Nations. Our country's parliament has risen to 37th place among 190 national parliaments in the world in terms of the number of women. , 49% of the members of the Democratic Party of Uzbekistan "National Revival" and the People's Democratic Party of Uzbekistan, 46% of the members of the Social Democratic Party of Uzbekistan "Adolat", Liberal Democratic Party of Uzbekistan women made up 41 percent of the members of the ecological party in Uzbekistan socio-economic policy at all stages of reforms included wide-ranging issues. Additional guarantees were given regarding the systematic increase of the population's income, the formation of employment and labor relations, the social protection and support of certain categories of the population, including women entrepreneurs and farmers"[1].

"In the parliamentary elections held on October 27, 2024, an important reform was carried out based on the fact that at least 40 percent of the candidates for deputies in Uzbekistan were women. This initiative was

remembered by the fact that 44.74% of the candidates for the parliamentary elections, and 42.45% for the deputies of the local councils were women. This indicator is a significant increase compared to the 30 percent quota recorded in the previous elections, and reflects the successful implementation of the country's struggle to increase the representation of women in governance." [2]

At the same time, women's participation in decision-making on current issues of state and community management is not sufficiently ensured, and their involvement in the socio-economic development of the regions remains weak.

Successful adaptation of women's activity in management to changing situations, clear direction of activity, proper formation of experience, qualifications and skills are the basis of effective activity in this regard.

By introducing the practice of active use of the institution of formation of women's personnel reserve, the range of opportunities for them to adequately serve the development of society and the management of society will expand. So, taking into account that the main "power" in moving every field is personnel, as a result of the introduction of the institution of formation of female personnel reserves, the methods and system of determining the socio-psychological characteristics of women will be formed.

Women's socio-political activity in the system of local state administration, representative bodies cooperating with it (Councils of People's Deputies) and self-governing bodies (neighborhood, citizens' assembly, committees for working with women, etc.) closely related to It can be said that the activities of women in this state administration system and civil society institutions are the most characteristic and widespread social and political activities of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The main goal is to ensure the rights and legal interests of women to a qualitatively new level, to strengthen their place and position in the family and society, to fully demonstrate their potential, to make the socio-spiritual environment in families healthier. is to create conditions for mobilisation. As a result of this, women of Uzbekistan are actively participating in the life of the state and society, their position in the family is being strengthened.

The socially oriented policy carried out by the head of our state creates the necessary opportunities for our women to live a truly happy life, to ensure their rights and freedoms, to develop intellectually and spiritually, and to fulfill their professional and family obligations in a coordinated manner.

Such mechanisms serve to ensure the effectiveness of achieving gender equality and the elimination of discrimination against women. Therefore, such

normative legal documents and practical measures are an important step in the field of gender policy of Uzbekistan, and it fully corresponds to international norms and standards of legislation and practice.

The sectors in which women participate the most and manage departments and directions in them are mainly social welfare (80%), culture and art (78%), public education (77%), health Health care (77%), wellness, mass sports (74%) are the fields.

A high state management system requires the ability to organize the activities of the entire network. It takes not only a lot of knowledge and strength, but also a lot of time. Women don't have that kind of time, they want to finish work as soon as possible and get home. That is why there is a shortage of female managers in higher state management systems (ministries, state committees).

At this point, the following points can be expressed. First of all, women who work in the higher state management system, who carry out management work, do not forget that there is a strict adherence to hierarchy and subordinate relations in the position. Secondly, they arise from the fact that personal initiative is not always supported, management activities require consultation with the top. This encourages them to be very careful. Thirdly, it is observed that they have not completely got rid of the tradition of following a man, living and working according to his advice. Today, both real life and scientific research show that the neighborhood, self-government bodies, civil institutions play an important role in social and political life, in increasing the activity of the population.

Local Councils of People's Deputies are the main force in solving territorial problems, the implementation of state and government decisions in real life largely depends on their activity. The Councils, which work together with the governors at the lower level of the state administration system, are the main force working with the population, labor unions, and civil society institutions. The transfer of some functions of state administration to local state administration bodies increases the influence of state representative institutions.

In conclusion, the most important direction of increasing the activity of women in the field of management is to form a new attitude to their education, to enlighten them, and to further increase their opportunities to become competitive personnel. In this matter, compliance with gender norms in the country is one of the important factors in solving existing problems.

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